

Ecosystem models based on hybrid vertical coordinates

by

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Preface

This report presents a class of biogeochemical models being coupled to the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM). The coupling has been done in a very general and flexible manner, to allow for an easy switching between formulations for the active ecosystem. Three different biochemical models have been embedded into the system; a simple 3-component NPZ type model, the classical FDM (Fasham-Ducklow-McKelvie) model, and a new formulation which has been developed by M. Schartau and coworkers through the ToP_AZ project. The HYCOM-Schartau model will constitute a state-of-the-art system for coupled simulations of the ocean physics and biochemical properties.

This document gives a detailed presentation of the coupling between HYCOM and the biochemistry. It will be illustrated that advection and mixing processes can be implemented in a general and “model independent” manner, together with a so-called regridding routine needed to redistribute the biochemical layer concentrations after each HYCOM regridding. The biochemical sources and sinks are of course model dependent; the three above mentioned formulations are briefly described.

The report does also contain detailed information about how the coupled HYCOM- ecosystem can be set up, compiled and run, including a short overview of the code distribution and the files (e.g., atmospheric forcing, bathymetry, etc.) necessary to run the model. Also, it is explained how a new biochemical module can be embedded into the system. Thus, the information should be of help for anyone interested in using and further extending the model system.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The requirements for the vertical discretization in ocean circulation models and models for the marine biogeochemistry generally differ. For example, while the circulation models often treat the surface ocean as a bulk mixed layer (e.g., MICOM), this is not appropriate for the marine ecosystem. Phytoplankton growth is dependent on the energy from the sun light, and the primary production is therefore confined to the few uppermost meters in the ocean. Thus, choosing the vertical discretization is not straight forward for a coupled physical-biochemical model system. One example is the use of density as the dependent vertical coordinate, i.e., an isopycnic discretization. Drange (1994) realized the above problems when coupling a biochemical model to the isopycnic coordinate MICOM model, and introduced a layer subsplitting procedure, i.e., to ensure a finer vertical resolution for the ecosystem in the physical mixed layer. This worked fine, but made the source code relatively complicated.

A recent improvement of the MICOM model has been the introduction of a hybrid vertical coordinate. The new HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) was first presented by Bleck (2002), and introduces a very flexible way of tuning the vertical discretization for a desired purpose. For example, the model uses ordinary z -layers in the physical mixed layer, and with a smooth transition it goes over to isopycnic coordinates in the deep ocean. This is appropriate also for a biochemical model, as long as the number of z -layers is sufficient for resolving the biochemical dynamics in the physical mixed layer.

This report summarizes the developments of a class of biochemical models coupled to the HYCOM model. The coupling is very flexible, and it should be relatively simple to introduce new biochemical formulations in the coupled system. One can also switch between different biochemical formulations just by setting a flag and recompiling, allowing for a direct comparison of the formulations using identical physical forcing, i.e., as provided by HYCOM.

In Chapter 2, the HYCOM model is shortly introduced. Then, the coupling with the biochemistry is explained in Chapter 3, dealing with “general” processes like mixing, advection and “ecosystem regridding”, as well as model dependent sources and sinks. Three formulations for the biochemistry are presented, and it is also illustrated that the system can be used for pure tracer simulations. A short summary is given in Chapter 4. Finally, a detailed description of the model code is provided

as appendices, and it is also briefly explained how to set up, compile and run a coupled HYCOM-biochemical model. Thus, this document may serve as a user's guide for the system.

Chapter 2

HYCOM

Ocean general circulation models have traditionally been categorized based on their vertical representation. For example, the most intuitive discretization is based on z -level coordinates, and other alternatives include terrain following σ -coordinates or isopycnal models using density as the vertical coordinate. It is obvious that no single vertical coordinate can by itself be optimal everywhere in the ocean. The different formulations are all able to simulate the large scale characteristics of the oceanic circulation reasonably well, but small scale (turbulent) processes will be very differently represented in the framework of different vertical discretizations. For example, the interior water mass distribution will to a large extent be influenced by local processes. Thus, models with different vertical discretizations have advantages and disadvantages depending on their applications. This motivates the development of a model with a “hybrid” vertical discretization, i.e., combining in the best possible way the advantages of the different formulations. A hybrid model can be used both in the open ocean and on the coastal shelves and it efficiently bridges the transition region between open ocean and coastal zones. An advanced ocean circulation model based on a hybrid vertical coordinate, the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model - HYCOM, has been developed by Bleck (2002). The HYCOM model has already been implemented and validated at NERSC in several projects, e.g., it is now used in the ToP_AZ operational ocean monitoring and prediction system.

During model evolution, the vertical discretization algorithm in HYCOM seeks for the “optimal” hybrid layer distribution at every time step. The algorithm chooses an isopycnal coordinate in the open ocean where the stratification is strong, with z -coordinates in the surface mixed layer or in regions with weak stratification. In coastal and shelf regions, the terrain following σ -coordinate is used. The transitions between the different coordinates are smooth, ensured by a so-called “cusion” function. To summarize, HYCOM chooses the “optimal” coordinate depending on the stratification and water depth, and performs a smooth transition of the layer profile and vertical characteristics of the water column from one regime to another.

An illustration of the hybrid vertical coordinate in HYCOM is given in Figure 2.1. The figure is a HYCOM forecast for January 1 2003 from the ToP_AZ real time experiment. The right plot shows a section in the Denmark Strait going between the two black dots indicated in the left map, respectively.

Figure 2.1: The section plot on the right is taken along the geodesic curve between the two black dots indicated in the left map. The section plot illustrates the hybrid vertical coordinate in HYCOM; the weakly stratified ocean mixed layer is resolved using a stack of z -layers, while the well stratified ocean interior is resolved using isopycnic coordinates. This example is taken from the real time experiment in ToPAZ and is the model forecast for January 1, 2003.

It is seen that the surface ocean mixed layer is resolved using a stack of relatively thin (10m) z -layers, while the well stratified ocean interior is resolved using isopycnic layers. Note that the user is free to specify the vertical discretization in HYCOM. For example, the number of z -layers in the upper ocean can be chosen, as well as the number of σ -layers in shallow water regions. One can even manipulate the coordinate setup to end up with a pure z -, σ - or isopycnic model if desirable. Thus, the hybrid coordinate setup is flexible and allows the user to decide the behavior.

Since HYCOM resolves the ocean mixed layer using level coordinates, one has the possibility to implement sophisticated schemes for the vertical mixing. Currently, two slab models of the Krauss-Turner type are implemented, as well as two sophisticated schemes which perform the mixing throughout the water column, i.e., treating the mixed layer as a non-slab vertical stack of z -layers. The standard algorithm is the k-profile parameterization (kpp) scheme by Large *et al.* (1994), with the level 2.5 turbulence closure algorithm of Mellor and Yamada (1982) as an alternative. Further schemes will probably be added in the future.

The vertical discretization in HYCOM is also ideal for running coupled simulations with biogeochemical models. Such models require relatively fine vertical resolution in the upper biologically active layer, and this is ensured since HYCOM chooses z -levels in the physical mixed layer. Further, isopycnic coordinates ensures a correct ventilation of deep water masses and, e.g., the supply of nutrients from the deep ocean. The coupling of HYCOM with models for the ocean biochemistry is further examined in the next chapter.

For information about (almost) all HYCOM details, please refer to Bleck *et al.* (2002).

Chapter 3

Biogeochemical models framed in hybrid vertical coordinates

This chapter deals with the coupling between HYCOM and models describing the ocean biogeochemistry. Section 3.1 describes the coupling in a general manner, i.e., without getting into biochemical model specific details. In Section 3.2, three different biochemical model formulations are described, and an overview of the corresponding model specific sources and sinks is provided.

3.1 Generally about the coupling between HYCOM and the biochemistry

Earlier developments of coupled physical-biochemical models based on isopycnic coordinates required advanced subsplitting of layers in order to resolve the ecosystem properly in the physical bulk mixed layer (see e.g. Drange, 1994, 1996). This is not necessary with HYCOM, since the physical mixed layer is explicitly resolved using ordinary z -levels. Thus, in the HYCOM-ecosystem formulation, the same hybrid layers are defined for both the physics and the ecosystem, i.e., simplifying the coupling. In HYCOM, one can manipulate the setup of the hybrid vertical coordinate, and this should be done to ensure a properly defined vertical resolution also for the biochemistry. The ecosystem is particularly active in the surface ocean in sufficient light conditions for phytoplankton to grow, i.e., the coupled model should have a well resolved vertical coordinate also in the physical mixed layer. This is ensured by a proper choice of z -layers for the hybrid coordinate.

The basic model equations in HYCOM can be found in Bleck (2002). In addition comes equations for the biochemistry; the transport of each biochemical tracer is described by an equation including the advection, mixing, flux terms and the sources and sinks of that particular tracer. Let each compartment concentration be denoted by C^i , and as in Bleck (2002), let us write the equations in (x, y, s) coordinates, where s is a general “hybrid” vertical coordinate. The transport of i th concentration

reads

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_s} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C^i \right) + \nabla_s \cdot \left(\mathbf{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C^i \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C^i \right) = \nabla_s \cdot \left(\nu \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \nabla_s C^i \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \mathcal{S}^i, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = (u, v)$ is the horizontal velocity vector, p is pressure, ν is the eddy viscosity/diffusivity coefficient, \dot{s} is the time derivative of s and \mathcal{S}^i represents the sources and sinks acting on the i th biochemical compartment. As in Bleck (2002), the subscript s indicates that this variable is held constant during differentiation. By integrating equation (3.1) over a coordinate layer bounded by the general coordinate surfaces s_{bot} and s_{top} , one gets an equation for the layer integrated transport, i.e.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} C^i \Delta p + \nabla_s \cdot (\mathbf{v} C^i \Delta p) + \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C^i \right)_{bot} - \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} C^i \right)_{top} = \nabla_s \cdot (\nu \Delta p \nabla_s C^i) + \Delta p \mathcal{S}^i. \quad (3.2)$$

An overview of how the terms in equation (3.2) are dealt with in the NERSC model system is given in the following.

The NERSC biochemical model system is illustrated in Figure 3.1; if a new ecosystem formulation is to be added to HYCOM, additional code must be added as indicated by the dark shaded boxes in the figure. The light shaded boxes are model independent; note in particular that the routines for the advection, mixing and regridding are model independent and that these need not be changed for a new ecosystem model. The figure indicates three different ecosystem models, one 3 component model (EVA85) based on Evans and Parslow (1985), one 11 compartment model (FDM02) based on Drange (1994, 1996) and a 7 compartment model (SCH02) which has been developed by our partners in EC-ToPAZ (the most recent version has 12 variables). Note that it is easy to switch between these models (just define a flag in *MODEL.CPP*, compile and run), and it is also a relatively simple task to add new ecosystem formulations at a later stage. The model independent routines for the advection, mixing and ecosystem “regridding” are described in the following three subsections 3.1.1, 3.1.2 and 3.1.3. Then, some general remarks are made about the sources and sinks in Section 3.1.4, followed by a comment about running the model as a pure tracer model in Subsection 3.1.5. Details about how to compile and run the code are included as separate appendices at the end of this report.

3.1.1 Horizontal advection and diffusion

In HYCOM, one has two options for the horizontal advection and diffusion:

1. Salinity is advected and temperature is diagnosed from the equation of state while maintaining isopycnic conditions.
2. Salinity and temperature are advected and with density diagnosed from the equation of state. Subsequent regridding will optimize isopycnic conditions in this case.

Embedding the ecosystem into the HYCOM horizontal advection/diffusion routine (*tsadv.c*) is relatively simple. In a loop over the number of biochemical compartments, the same procedure as used for the physics can be used for each biochemical tracer. This means that the implementation is only

Figure 3.1: The NERSC biochemical model system is programmed such that one easily can switch between different formulations for the ecosystem, and new formulations can easily be added. The user defines which model to compile and run through a flag in the file MODEL.CPP, which is used by the makefile. If a new model is to be implemented in the HYCOM-ecosystem system, the number of compartments and a short character model flag is defined in the module containing the necessary definitions. Then, all the compartments will be stored in the variable bio. All additional specific variables and model parameters are gathered in separate modules for the particular model. The most important property of the system, is that the routines for advection, mixing and the ecosystem regridding are model independent, just defining loops over the number of tracer variables. Note also that these routines are not dependent on the model dependent definitions in the top-right box. The only model specific routine, is the call for the sources and the sinks. Note that three different biochemical formulations are shown in the figure (EVA85, FDM02, SCH02), but any number of formulations can be added. Then, once the user has made a choice for a model flag in MODEL.CPP, the correct formulation will be compiled and run. In this way, it will be both easy and flexible to run and compare different formulations of the ecosystem with HYCOM.

dependent on the number of tracers, and it can be made general and model independent. Details about the standard advection routine in HYCOM can be found in Bleck *et al.* (2002).

The ecosystem (tracer) advection was first implemented for the standard second order advection scheme in the HYCOM code distribution. A “noise free” fourth order advection scheme has recently been developed at NERSC by Y. Morel and coworkers, and has proven to be superior to the standard HYCOM approach. The new scheme ensures much smoother fields, i.e., allowing for a reduction of the grid resolution without any information loss in the model fields. Thus, even though the new scheme is numerically heavier to run, one can still save computing time by decreasing the grid resolution. The fourth order scheme has recently been updated to include the ecosystem, and this should now be used as the standard approach.

3.1.2 Vertical mixing

The vertical mixing of the biochemistry has been implemented for the Large *et al.* (1994) KPP (K-Profile Parameterization) scheme. Alternative schemes have recently been proposed by the HYCOM community, but KPP is still the state-of-the-art standard routine used.

The mixing of the biochemistry can also be implemented in a general and model independent manner. The framework of KPP for a general tracer concentration C^i is considered in the following. We start by decomposing the tracer into mean and turbulent parts;

$$C^i = \overline{C^i} + C^{i'}, \quad (3.3)$$

where the overbar denotes the mean and the prime a turbulent perturbation, respectively. Standard Reynolds averaging rules apply, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{C^{i'}} &= \overline{C^{j'}} = 0, \\ \overline{C^i C^j} &= \overline{C^i} \overline{C^j} + \overline{C^{i'} C^{j'}}, \\ \overline{C^{i'} C^j} &= \overline{C^{j'} C^i} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where i and j refer to two different tracers. By inserting (3.3) into the transport equations (3.2), and averaging, one will find an equation for the mean motion. The resulting vertical diffusion equation reads

$$\frac{\partial \overline{C^i}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{w' C^{i'}}, \quad (3.4)$$

where w' is the vertical turbulent velocity.

In the K-Profile Parameterization (KPP) vertical mixing scheme, the diffusivity $\overline{w' C^{i'}}$ is explicitly and differently modelled in the turbulent mixed layer and the ocean interior, and the two regimes are then matched at the boundary. In the turbulent mixed layer, the diffusivity can be expressed as

$$\overline{w' C^{i'}} = -K_{C^i} \left(\frac{\partial \overline{C^i}}{\partial z} + \gamma_{C^i} \right), \quad (3.5)$$

where $-K_{C^i}$ is the diffusivity parameter for C^i and γ_{C^i} is a non-local flux term which kick in when the surface forcing is destabilizing. The nonlocal fluxes are set to zero for the biochemistry as for any other tracer in HYCOM. The diffusivity in the ocean interior reads

$$\overline{w' C^{i'}} = -\nu_{C^i} \frac{\partial \overline{C^i}}{\partial z}, \quad (3.6)$$

where ν_{C^i} is the interior diffusivity parameter.

Let us now consider how the surface and interior diffusivity parameter profiles are matched. Let \mathcal{K} be the composed (surface and interior) diffusivity parameter profile, and assume it can be written as

$$\mathcal{K}_{C^i}(\sigma) = h_c w_{C^i}(\sigma) f_{C^i}(\sigma), \quad (3.7)$$

where h_c is a critical depth parameter dependent on the strength of the mixed layer turbulence, w_{C^i} is a velocity scale, σ is the potential density and f is the function

$$f(\sigma) = a_0 + a_1\sigma + a_2\sigma^2 + a_3\sigma^3. \quad (3.8)$$

In equation (3.8), a_0 , a_1 , a_2 and a_3 are unknown parameters to be determined. Turbulent eddies do not cross the ocean surface, which means that

$$\mathcal{K}_{C^i}(0) = 0, \quad (3.9)$$

giving $a_0 = 0$. The other two coefficients are chosen in order to ensure matching values and first order vertical derivatives between the interior and boundary layer profiles $\mathcal{K} = K_{C^i}$ and $\mathcal{K} = \nu_{C^i}$ at the critical depth h_c . Further details on the procedure can be found in Bleck *et al.* (2002).

As for the advection scheme, the vertical mixing is implemented in a general tracer loop over the number of biochemical compartments.

3.1.3 Ecosystem regridding

In every time step of the model evolution, HYCOM performs a regridding of the hybrid vertical coordinates. This procedure tries to keep the potential density of every HYCOM layer as close as possible to the “target” density of the layer. This cannot always be exactly satisfied because of the hybrid layer constraints imposed on the vertical coordinate distribution, e.g., z -layers with constant thickness are chosen in the mixed layer and σ -layers in shallow waters, suppressing the possibility to stay close to the target density. A detailed description of the hybrid layer generator in HYCOM (*hybgen.f*) is described in detail in Bleck *et al.* (2002). For our purpose it is sufficient to know that the routine redistributes the vertical coordinate in every time step by moving upwards or downwards the layer interfaces in the model.

A redistribution of the vertical coordinate surfaces makes it necessary to update the tracer concen-

Figure 3.2: Case 1.

trations according to the new layers. The procedure described in the following may be implemented for any tracer variable. Note also that it may be used for any vertical coordinate regenerator, since it works on the “old” and “new” layer distributions directly. That is, the routine needs to know the old and new interface pressures, as well as the tracer concentration according to the old layer profile, but no information is required about how the new layer profile was generated. A description of the algorithm now follows.

Let C_i denote the tracer concentration in old layer i (i.e., before *hybgen.f* has been called), and C'_k the tracer concentration in new layer k (i.e., after *hybgen.f* has been called), with the prime referring to updated concentrations. Further, let p be a pressure level in the water column. Assume that we are updating the tracer concentrations from top to bottom, and that we are about to start updating the concentration C'_k in new layer k . Let C_{ini} be the concentration in the first old layer which affects the update of C'_k , and C_{final} the concentration in the last old layer affecting C'_k , respectively. The following three situations may occur:

Case 1: In this case, which is shown in Figure 3.2, the new layer is completely embraced by the old, and we get that $C'_k = C_{ini}$.

Case 2: This case, which involves two old layers in the update of C'_k , is illustrated in Figure 3.3. Constancy of matter between pressure levels p_k and p_{k+1} gives that

$$C_{ini} (p_{ini+1} - p_k) + C_{ini+1} (p_{k+1} - p_{ini+1}) = C'_k (p_{k+1} - p_k), \quad (3.10)$$

and solving for C'_k this gives

$$C'_k = \frac{C_{ini} (p_{ini+1} - p_k) + C_{ini+1} (p_{k+1} - p_{ini+1})}{p_{k+1} - p_k}. \quad (3.11)$$

Case 3: In this case, three or more old layers are involved in the update of C'_k (see Figure 3.4). Again, constancy of matter between pressure levels p_k and p_{k+1} , and then solving for C'_k gives that

$$C'_k = \frac{1}{p_{k+1} - p_k} [C_{ini} (p_{ini+1} - p_k) + C_{ini+1} (p_{ini+2} - p_{ini+1}) + \dots]$$

Figure 3.3: Case 2.

$$+ C_{final-1} (p_{final} - p_{final-1}) + C_{final} (p_{k+1} - p_{final})]. \quad (3.12)$$

A short summary of the complete algorithm is as follows:

```

subroutine regrid_ecosys(p_old,p_new,biofield)
  real, intent(in) :: p_old(idm,jdm,kdm+1) !interface pressure, old grid
  real, intent(in) :: p_new(idm,jdm,kdm+1) !interface pressure, new grid
  real, intent(inout) :: biofield(nbio,2*kdm,idm,jdm) !to be 'regridded'

  do j=1,jdm
  do i=1,idm
    <extract column i,j from p_old, p_new and biofield>

    do k=1,kdm !loop over the new layer distribution
      <count the number of old layers involved in the update of new layer k>
      <select case 1, 2 or 3 and calculate the updated tracer concentration>
    enddo !k

    <put updated k-column back into the biofield variable>
  enddo !i
  enddo !j
end subroutine regrid_ecosys

```

The remaining problem is then to find out how many old layers are involved in the update of new layer k . Note that the k -loop is over the new layers, for which the tracer concentrations are updated from top to bottom. For iteration k , one can count the old layers involved in the update of new layer k , and save the index for the lower old layer until next iteration $k+1$. The procedure is best illustrated by looking at the complete source code which now follows:

Figure 3.4: Case 3.

```

subroutine regrid_ecosys(p_ol,p_new,biofield)
  use mod_common
  use mod_necessary_ecovars
  implicit none

  real, intent(in) :: p_ol(idm,jdm,kdm+1)      !interface pressure, old grid
  real, intent(in) :: p_new(idm,jdm,kdm+1)      !interface pressure, new grid
  real, intent(inout) :: biofield(nbio,2*kdm,idm,jdm) !to be 'regridded'

  real bio_old(nbio,kdm) !holds one column of the old tracer distribution
  real bio_new(nbio,kdm) !holds one column of the updated tracer distribution
  real p_old_k(kdm+1)      !holds one column of the old pressure profile
  real p_new_k(kdm+1)      !holds one column of the new pressure profile

  !counters...
  integer lay_old1 !initial old layer involved in the update of k-th new layer
  integer lay_old2 !final old layer involved in the update of k-th new layer
  integer delta_old !nu. of old layers involved in updating the k-th new layer
  integer k, i, j, ilay

  logical count_true
  real    sum(nbio)          !tmp workspace
  real    eps, eps_bottompressure !small values

  eps = 1.0e-8

  do j=1,jdm
  do i=1,idm

  !-----
  !extracting the k-th column vectors...
  do k=1,kdm
    bio_old(:,k) = biofield(:,k,i,j)
    bio_new(:,k) = 0.0 !to be updated
  enddo
  p_old_k(:) = p_ol(i,j,:)
  p_new_k(:) = p_new(i,j,:)
  !-----

  !-----
  !Checking consistency of bottom pressure in old and new p-profiles...
  if (p_new_k(kdm+1) /= p_old_k(kdm+1)) then
    print *, 'i,j: ',i,j
    print *, 'WARNING ECO REGRIDDING: '
    print *, 'incosistent bottom pressures in p_old_k vs. p_new_k: '
    print *, '                ', p_old_k(kdm+1), p_new_k(kdm+1)
    eps_bottompressure = abs(p_new_k(kdm+1) - p_old_k(kdm+1))
  
```

```

if (eps_bottompressure < eps) then
  print *, 'eps < ', eps, '; setting p_new_k = p_old_k'
  p_new_k(kdm+1) = p_old_k(kdm+1)
else
  print *, 'STOP eco regridding: eps = ', eps_bottompressure
  stop
endif
endif
!-----

lay_old1=1 !starting to count the surface old layer

do k=1,kdm !loop over new layer distribution
  !For layer k, the tracer concentration is to be updated
  !New layer k includes old layers with indices from lay_old1 to lay_old2
  !At step k, lay_old1 has initially the index of lay_old2 from step k-1

  !-----
  !initializing...
  lay_old2 = lay_old1 !lay_old2 is to be counted; initializing with lay_old1
  delta_old = 1 !also to be counted
  count_true = .false.
  !-----

  !-----
  !Counting the number of old layers involved in new layer k update
  if (p_new_k(k+1) > p_old_k(lay_old2+1)) then
    !more than 1 old layer involved...
    count_true = .true.
    do
      if (.not. count_true) exit
      lay_old2 = lay_old2 + 1
      delta_old = delta_old + 1
      if (p_new_k(k+1) <= p_old_k(lay_old2+1)) then
        !last old layer involved in new layer k
        count_true = .false.
      endif
    enddo
  endif
endif
!-----

!-----
if (delta_old == 1) then
  !The new layer is bracketed by the old -> no correction...
  do ibio=1, nbio
    bio_new(ibio,k) = bio_old(ibio,lay_old2)
  enddo
endif

```

```

else if (delta_old == 2) then
!Two old layers involved...
  do ibio = 1,nbio
    bio_new(ibio,k)=&
      (bio_old(ibio,lay_old1)*(p_old_k(lay_old1+1)-p_new_k(k))&
      +bio_old(ibio,lay_old2)*(p_new_k(k+1)-p_old_k(lay_old1+1)))&
      /(p_new_k(k+1)-p_new_k(k))
  enddo

else
!Three or more old layers involved...
  sum(:) = 0.0
  do ilay = lay_old1+1, lay_old2-1
    !old layers completely within new layer k...
    do ibio=1,nbio
      sum(ibio)=sum(ibio)+bio_old(ibio,ilay)*(p_old_k(ilay+1)-p_old_k(ilay))
    enddo
  enddo
  do ibio=1,nbio
    bio_new(ibio,k)=&
      (bio_old(ibio,lay_old1)*(p_old_k(lay_old1+1)-p_new_k(k))&
      +sum(ibio) &
      +bio_old(ibio,lay_old2)*(p_new_k(k+1)-p_old_k(lay_old2)))&
      /(p_new_k(k+1)-p_new_k(k))
  enddo
endif
!-----

  lay_old1 = lay_old2 !initial old layer for next new layer k+1

enddo !k-loop

do k=1,kdm
  biofield(:,k,i,j) = bio_new(:,k) !regridded fields as output from routine
enddo

enddo !i-loop
enddo !j-loop

end subroutine regrid_ecosys

```

In the above algorithm, *lay_old1* and *lay_old2* keep track of the upper and lower old layer involved in the update of new layer *k*, respectively, with *delta_old* being the number of old layers. Note that the concentrations are updated column by column from surface to bottom, i.e., starting to calculate the concentrations in the surface new layer. The counting of old layers involved in the update is done

in the following way:

- Before each k -loop, lay_old1 is initialized to 1, i.e., the index of the surface old layer.
- Then, the k -loop is entered, and one starts by setting lay_old2 equal to lay_old1 .
- Next, lay_old2 is updated in a loop, until the lower interface pressure of old layer lay_old2 has reached the lower interface pressure of new layer k .
- When lay_old1 and lay_old2 are known, one can update the concentrations in new layer k according to one of the above mentioned cases 1, 2 or 3.
- At the end of each k iteration, lay_old1 is set to lay_old2 , i.e., initializing the upper old layer for the next iteration $k + 1$.

Note that the above presented algorithm is general and independent of the hybrid regenerator routine used in HYCOM. Input to the procedure are the old and new interface pressures, as well as the old tracer concentrations, and this information is sufficient to update the tracers according to the new (regridded) vertical layers.

3.1.4 Generally about the sources and sinks

In addition to “general” processes like advection and mixing, there will be various model specific sources and sinks for the different biochemical tracers. For example, phytoplankton generally synthesize energy from different nutrients through photosynthesis, leading to a growing stock. Furthermore, phytoplankton are eaten by zooplankton, or may suffer from unfavorable physical or nutrient conditions. Zooplankton are eaten by organisms at higher trophic levels, and so on. All dead organisms are either being remineralised by bacteria, or they sink towards the bottom where they also are remineralised slowly. Thus, the bacteria play an important role in a closed ecosystem.

The natural ecosystems are very complex and therefore hard to model in general. Thus, we have to simplify the real world. Very often, it is the flow of matter through the ecosystem we are interested in, and not the standing stocks of the specific compartments. For example, this is true for the many models which are designed to simulate and quantify the oceanic sink of CO_2 .

Since the biochemical sources and sinks will vary between different model formulations, we wanted to create a coupled system for which we easily could switch between different formulations for the active ecosystem. In equation (3.2) describing the transport of the biochemical compartments, the only model specific term is \mathcal{S} , which contains the ecosystem sources and sinks. Thus, the calculation of \mathcal{S} is better contained in one model specific routine. In Section 3.2, three different formulations for the active biochemistry are described; a simple NPZ-type model, a classical model often referred to as FDM (Fasham-Ducklow-McKelvie), as well as a model being developed in the ToPAZ project.

3.1.5 A pure tracer model

An immediate consequence of \mathcal{S} being calculated in a separate routine is that the call for this can be turned off. That is, \mathcal{S} is set to zero, and the model is reduced to a classical “passive” tracer model. This can be used to follow a released blob of water, i.e., to see how it spreads out and is advected with the water flow with time. For example, this could be used to follow and predict the tracer concentration in case of a toxic event, one could predict the evolution of oil slicks, or one could use the model to study the pathways of *in situ* floats.

3.2 Three formulations for the active biochemistry

This section contains a description of three different formulations for the active biochemical system and its sources and sinks (EVA85, FDM02, and SCH02). All three models are typically “open ocean” models, i.e., developed to describe the large scale variations of the ecosystem in open ocean domains. For any specific coastal application, one will have to include dynamical properties of the ecosystem which are locally important. For example, one will in many coastal and shelf domains need to include a description of the benthic ecosystem.

Additional information about the EVA85 formulation can be found in Evans and Parslow (1985); Natvik *et al.* (2001), while FDM is described and discussed in Fasham *et al.* (1990); Drange (1994, 1996); Natvik (2001); Natvik and Evensen (2003a,b). The SCH02 model is not yet published elsewhere, but will be included in the ToPAZ report.

3.2.1 The EVA85 formulation

This formulation is based on the classical paper by Evans and Parslow (1985), who presented the model in a zero-dimensional framework, which means that they studied the time evolution of the compartments without including spatial variations. The model is ideal for the beginner to learn about simple marine ecosystem dynamics, and it also forms an important basis for more complex dynamical formulations. Only three biochemical compartments are included; one single nutrient pool, as well as one phytoplankton and one zooplankton component. The compartments should be regarded as averaged representatives over the large number of actual species in the ocean. An illustration of the dynamical system is illustrated in Figure 3.5, note that advection and mixing processes come in addition. At the base of the ecosystem, phytoplankton utilizes the energy from the sun light to grow on nutrients (through photosynthesis). Phytoplankton losses, including mortality and exudation, are immediately remineralized back to nutrients using a constant factor. Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton, and is grazed by higher order predators. The latter acts as a closure of the model, since zooplankton is the highest order trophic level explicitly included. The sources and sinks in equation (3.2) for the EVA85 model for nutrients N , phytoplankton P and zooplankton Z can be written

Figure 3.5: The EVA85 model is the simplest example of a NPZ-type formulation. As indicated from the figure, phytoplankton synthesize energy from the sun and utilize nitrates in the growth process. Furthermore, zooplankton feed on phytoplankton, while the ecosystem is closed by including a large loss term on the highest order trophic level (zooplankton). Note that mixing and advection processes come in addition.

as

$$S_{EVA85}^N = - \left(\frac{\alpha(t, P)N}{j + N} - r \right) P, \quad (3.13)$$

$$S_{EVA85}^P = \left(\frac{\alpha(t, P)N}{j + N} - r \right) P - \frac{c(P - P_0)Z}{K + P - P_0}, \quad (3.14)$$

$$S_{EVA85}^Z = \frac{fc(P - P_0)Z}{K + P - P_0} - gZ, \quad (3.15)$$

where $\alpha(t, P)$ is the photosynthetic (light limited) growth rate and j, r, c, P_0, K, f and g are constants explained in the following. The formulation of the growth processes follows the now well accepted Michaelis-Menten (M-M) approach, for which a maximum growth rate is reduced by a hyperbolic unitless fraction. The M-M approach is generally accepted for many processes, and there seems to be a good agreement with empirical data both in laboratory and in real ecosystems (see Goldberg *et al.*, 1977; Kremer and Nixon, 1978, and references therein). For example, in equation (3.14), α is the growth rate of phytoplankton under maximum nutrient availability, while the nutrient limitation is included in the hyperbolic expression $N/j + N$ with j being the half saturation constant of nutrient limited phytoplankton growth. A similar expression is used for zooplankton growth, with c being a maximum grazing rate, f is a grazing efficiency parameter, P_0 is a lower bound of phytoplankton on the zooplankton grazing and K is a half saturation constant, respectively. Metabolism of phytoplankton is modelled as a linear term with r being the loss parameter, and a similar expression is used for the zooplankton losses with g being the loss rate, respectively. The numerical values of the

parameters can be found in Evans and Parslow (1985), while the light model used for calculating α is the same as that used in the FDM model (see the next section).

The annual cycle of the model is as follows. During winter, deep nutrients are mixed to the surface ocean. Then, during spring when the light level increases and the temperature rises, the phytoplankton starts to grow on the nutrients. In the time frame of just a few days, a phytoplankton spring bloom develops, and is closely followed by a corresponding zooplankton bloom. Note that when the phytoplankton bloom has reached the maximum, the nutrient availability is very limited, and the stocks of plankton collapse. During winter, the nutrient concentrations start to build up again, closing the annual loop.

The EVA85 model has very simple dynamics, and it is therefore an ideal formulation to start out with, both to learn about the behavior of “typical” ecosystem Michaelis-Menten type relations, and also because it is a simple model to start out with in the debugging process in the coupled system. In fact, the FDM model presented next is based on the EVA85 model, but has more compartments and is better suited for accurate simulations of the open ocean ecosystem.

3.2.2 The FDM02 formulation

The FDM model is based on the classical ecosystem model first presented by Fasham *et al.* (1990) and the chemical model by Peng *et al.* (1987). The model was further developed and coupled to MICOM by Drange (1994, 1996), and the coupled isopycnic FDM model has been used at NERSC for almost a decade. The model presented here is strongly based on the FDM version by Drange (1996), but simplified and rewritten for use in the hybrid framework. A rather detailed summary of the model sources and sinks is given below; and the photic zone ecosystem is illustrated in Figure 3.6.

The following eleven biochemical compartments are explicitly modelled;

Phytoplankton	P ,
Zooplankton	Z ,
Bacteria	B ,
Nitrate	N_n ,
Ammonium	N_r ,
Dissolved organic nitrogen (DON)	N_d ,
Dissolved organic carbon (DOC)	C_d ,
Detritus; particulate organic nitrogen (PON)	D_N ,
Detritus; particulate organic carbon (POC)	D_C ,
Dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC)	C_T ,
Alkalinity	A_T .

The nitrogen based compartments are given in terms of mmol N m^{-3} (millimoles of nitrogen per cubic meter) and the carbon based in terms of mmol C m^{-3} (millimoles of carbon per cubic meter),

Figure 3.6: A schematic representation of the photic zone biochemical system in the FDM model. Primary production is fuelled by nitrate (1) and ammonium (6), and reduced by phytoplankton exudation (4) and mortality (5). Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton (7), bacteria (12) and detritus (13) with prescribed efficiencies, and the fecal pellets represent a sink to detritus (14). Further, zooplankton losses (excretion, mortality, messy ingestion, Redfield balance term, grazing by higher predators, etc.) are split up as sinks to ammonium (11), dissolved organic matter (8) and an export term representing large sinking particles (9). The bacteria take up ammonium (17) and dissolved organic matter (18), and excrete ammonium (16). Particulate matter may sink (23) or may be broken down to dissolved matter (22). The concentration of dissolved inorganic carbon decreases during photosynthesis (3) and during formation of CaCO_3 (24), and increases during zooplankton and bacterial excretion (10, 19). Alkalinity increases during nitrate fuelled and decreases during ammonium fuelled primary production (2). Further, zooplankton and bacterial excretion increase the alkalinity (15, 21), while bacterial uptake of ammonium and the formation of CaCO_3 decrease A_T (20, 25).

respectively. The alkalinity is expressed as charge equivalents meq m^{-3} (for ion X^q , where q is the charge, 1 mole corresponds to $|q|$ equivalents).

Nitrogen is used as the basis model currency. As pointed out by Fasham *et al.* (1990), this allows primary production to be partitioned into new production fuelled by nitrate and regenerated production fuelled by ammonium. Further, nitrogen is generally regarded as the limiting nutrient of primary production.

Different biochemical model formulations are used in the photic zone and at greater depths, respectively. In the photic zone, the exchanges of nitrogen can be described by simple dynamical relations between the compartments included in the active ecosystem. A simple nutrient regeneration model is used below the photic zone. Normally, the photic or euphotic zone is defined as the zone in which there is a net primary production (see e.g. Bearman *et al.*, 1995). Thus, by definition the ecosystem cannot survive for long below the photic zone. In our model formulation, the photic zone is defined as the penetration depth of 75% of the surface irradiance, but with a predefined minimum of 40 m (Drange, 1994).

A brief description of the biochemical sources and sinks (i.e. the last term of equations (3.2)) will now be given, starting with the photic zone (which is illustrated in Figure 3.6);

The photic zone ecosystem

The evolution of **phytoplankton** P is described by the following equation;

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^P = (1 - \gamma) \sigma(t, z, N_n, N_r) P - G_1 - \mu_1 \frac{P^2}{k_5 + P}. \quad (3.16)$$

In the above formulation, γ represents the net exudation of the total primary production as dissolved organic nitrogen, $\sigma(t, z, N_n, N_r)$ is the phytoplankton growth rate and G_1 is the loss of phytoplankton due to zooplankton grazing. A hyperbolic Michaelis-Menten type relation is used as the last term in (3.16) to describe the mortality of phytoplankton. In this term, μ_1 is the specific (max) mortality rate and k_5 is the half saturation constant for phytoplankton mortality, respectively.

It is assumed that the limitation of phytoplankton growth due to light and nutrients can be decoupled, i.e.,

$$\sigma(t, z, N_n, N_r) = J(t, z) \tilde{N}(N_n, N_r), \quad (3.17)$$

where J is the light limited growth rate and \tilde{N} is the nutrient limitation. Further, we assume that the nutrient limitation can be expressed as

$$\tilde{N}(N_n, N_r) = \tilde{N}_n(N_n, N_r) + \tilde{N}_r(N_r), \quad (3.18)$$

where

$$\tilde{N}_n(N_n, N_r) = \frac{N_n \exp(-\psi N_r)}{k_1 + N_n}, \quad (3.19)$$

$$\tilde{N}_r(N_r) = \frac{N_r}{k_2 + N_r}, \quad (3.20)$$

and k_1 and k_2 are the half saturation constants for nitrate and ammonium uptake, respectively. Phytoplankton tends to prefer ammonium over nitrate, which has been parameterized by the exponential term in (3.19) with ψ as a characteristic inhibition parameter.

The relation between irradiance Q and photosynthesis is parameterized as

$$F(Q) = V_p \frac{\alpha Q}{\sqrt{V_p^2 + \alpha^2 Q^2}}, \quad (3.21)$$

where V_p is the max rate and α is the initial slope of the photosynthesis-irradiance curve. The light limited growth rate of phytoplankton may then be expressed as a function of F ;

$$J(t, z) = F \left(Q_d \exp \left(\frac{-k_t z}{\cos \theta_d} \right) + Q_s \left(\frac{-k_t z}{\mu} \right) \right), \quad (3.22)$$

where Q_d represents direct sun light and Q_s diffuse sky light, respectively. Further, θ_d is the sun zenith angle of direct sun light in water, while μ is a mean value of the zenith angles of diffuse sky light. Both water and phytoplankton contribute to the total attenuation k_t , i.e.,

$$k_t = k_w + k_c P(z), \quad (3.23)$$

where k_w and k_c are the attenuation coefficients of water and phytoplankton (i.e. self shading), respectively. A detailed description of the irradiance model used will not be given here, an interested reader should see Drange (1994). It is worth mentioning, however, that the model (including cloud effects) must be expected to have errors of about 20% in the irradiance field.

The **zooplankton** compartment evolves according to;

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^Z = \beta_1 G_1 + \beta_2 G_2 + \beta_3 G_3 - \mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z} - E_{don}. \quad (3.24)$$

Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton, bacteria and particulate organic matter (detritus), respectively. The grazing on the three different sources of food is parameterized by the grazing rates G_1 , G_2 and G_3 with corresponding prescribed assimilation efficiencies β_1 , β_2 and β_3 . The fourth term on the right hand side is a Michaelis-Menten type term representing zooplankton losses. The loss rate μ_2 , which includes both excretion and mortality, is split into three parts, i.e. we let δ be in the form of DON, ϵ in the form of ammonium and $1 - \delta - \epsilon$ is the part which is immediately exported out of the photic zone (Drange, 1994). Zooplankton excrete both ammonium and DON, and ‘‘messy’’ ingestion causes a breakdown of cells into DON (Fasham *et al.*, 1990). Further, dead zooplankton become detritus, which may be decomposed to DON or sink out of the photic zone. Note also that the fourth term acts as a closure term of the ecosystem, representing predation by higher order organisms (Fasham *et al.*,

1990). The last term in (3.24) represents a sink to DON, in order to maintain a constant zooplankton Redfield ratio.

Let us consider the derivation of the grazing function of zooplankton on phytoplankton, namely G_1 . We start by defining the total available food for zooplankton as

$$F = p'_1 P + p'_2 B + p'_3 D_N, \quad (3.25)$$

where p'_1 , p'_2 and p'_3 are preference functions for the three types of food. As in Fasham *et al.* (1990), we allow the zooplankton compartment to graze on the most abundant source of food, based on constant “background” preferences p_1 , p_2 and p_3 . This is equivalent to assuming that there always exists some particular group of the complex zooplankton compartment, which will grow on the most abundant type of food (Fasham *et al.*, 1990). The preference for phytoplankton, p'_1 , can now be written as

$$p'_1 = \frac{p_1 P}{(p_1 P + p_2 B + p_3 D_N)}. \quad (3.26)$$

For information on different types of preference functions, see Fasham *et al.* (1990). By defining the grazing rate of zooplankton on phytoplankton as

$$G_1 = gZ \frac{p'_1 P}{k_3 + F}, \quad (3.27)$$

and by defining corresponding expressions for G_2 and G_3 , a standard Michaelis-Menten formulation for the total grazing is ensured. That is,

$$G_1 + G_2 + G_3 = g \frac{F}{k_3 + F} Z, \quad (3.28)$$

where g is the max rate and k_3 is the half saturation constant for zooplankton grazing, respectively. By inserting equation (3.25) and (3.26) into (3.27), we get the following expression for the zooplankton grazing on phytoplankton;

$$G_i = gZ p_1 \frac{P^2}{k_3 (p_1 P + p_2 B + p_3 D_N) + p_1 P^2 + p_2 B^2 + p_3 D_N^2}. \quad (3.29)$$

Corresponding expressions for G_2 and G_3 can be found in a similar manner.

In the Drange (1994) model, the Redfield carbon to nitrogen ratios of phytoplankton (R_p) and zooplankton (R_z) were assumed equal, while a lower bacterial ratio (R_b) was used. To get a balanced flow of carbon and nitrogen through the zooplankton compartment, Drange (1994) introduced an additional ammonium excretion term for zooplankton grazing on bacteria. In the present model formulation (Drange, 1996), the Redfield ratios R_p , R_z and R_b all have different numerical values. In addition, carbon based compartments for organic dissolved material (DOC) and particulate matter (POC) have been included explicitly in the model, assuming “free floating” carbon to nitrogen

ratios for DOM and POM. Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton, bacteria and detritus with carbon to nitrogen ratios R_p , R_b and R_{dom} , respectively. To maintain a constant carbon to nitrogen ratio for zooplankton, excess nitrogen is in the current model simply turned over to DON (the term E_{don} in (3.24)) and excess carbon to DOC, respectively (Drange, 1995).

The equation for the evolution of **bacteria** is

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^B = U_1 + U_2 - \mu_3 B - G_2, \quad (3.30)$$

where U_1 is the bacterial uptake of DON, U_2 is the uptake of ammonium and μ_3 is the specific excretion rate, respectively.

Drange (1994) reformulated the expressions for U_1 and U_2 given in Fasham *et al.* (1990), based on the fact that the Fasham *et al.* (1990) formulation did not maintain a constant bacterial carbon to nitrogen ratio for small ammonium concentrations. As mentioned above, the current model includes DOC and POC, with free floating DOC/DON and POC/PON Redfield ratios. This can be used to derive (Michaelis-Menten) type formulations for U_1 and U_2 , based on the non-accumulating flow of nitrogen and carbon through the bacterial pool (see Drange (1995) for the detailed formulation).

The **particulate organic nitrogen** equation can be written as

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{D_N} = (1 - \beta_1) G_1 + (1 - \beta_2) G_2 + (1 - \beta_3) G_3 - G_3 + \mu_1 \frac{P^2}{k_5 + P} - \mu_4 D_N - w \frac{\partial D_N}{\partial z}, \quad (3.31)$$

where μ_4 is the specific breakdown rate of detritus (to DON), and w is a characteristic sinking rate of the detrital compartment. The first three terms on the right hand side of (3.31) represent the fecal pellets of zooplankton grazing on phytoplankton, bacteria and detritus, respectively. Further, the fourth term represents the loss to zooplankton, the fifth is the source from dead phytoplankton, the sixth is the detrital breakdown to DON and the last term represents the sinking of detrital matter.

The corresponding equation for **particulate organic carbon** is similar, using the Redfield ratios of each compartment to convert nitrogen to carbon.

The **nitrate** equation can be written as

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{N_n} = -J(t, z) \tilde{N}_n P. \quad (3.32)$$

Thus, the only sink is due to uptake by the phytoplankton compartment. As mentioned in Fasham *et al.* (1990), the use of nitrogen as the base model currency leads to the natural distinction between new and regenerated production. The former is fuelled by nitrate, while the latter is fuelled by ammonium regenerated in the model for the photic zone.

The **ammonium** equation reads

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{N_r} = -J(t, z) \tilde{N}_r P - U_2 + \mu_3 B + \epsilon \mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z}, \quad (3.33)$$

where the two first terms on the right hand side represent the loss to phytoplankton and bacteria, respectively. The third and fourth terms are sources due to bacterial excretion and due to losses of zooplankton, respectively.

The evolution of **dissolved organic nitrogen** is described by;

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{N_d} = \gamma J(t, z) (\tilde{N}_n + \tilde{N}_r) P + \delta \mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z} + \mu_4 D_N - U_1 + E_{don}. \quad (3.34)$$

The first term on the right hand side is the phytoplankton exudation, the second represents zooplankton losses, the third is the breakdown of detritus, while the fourth is the bacterial uptake of DON. The fifth is a source from zooplankton, ensuring a constant Redfield ratio R_z .

Again, the equation for **dissolved organic carbon** is similar, using the Redfield ratios of the different compartments to convert nitrogen to carbon.

As in Drange (1994), it is assumed that phytoplankton is the only compartment capable of fixing **inorganic carbon** C_T . Thus, C_T is lost during photosynthesis due to the Redfield carbon to nitrogen ratio of phytoplankton. One concentration unit of C_T is also lost during formation of one corresponding unit of calcium carbonate CaCO_3 . Further, bacterial and zooplankton excretion lead to increased carbon concentrations. The inorganic carbon equation now reads

$$\mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{C_T} = -J(t, z) (\tilde{N}_n + \tilde{N}_r) P R_p - \frac{\delta \text{CaCO}_3}{\delta t} + \mu_3 B R_b + \epsilon \mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z} R_z. \quad (3.35)$$

The treatment of the CO_2 gas exchange at the air-water boundary, and adjustments due to evaporation, precipitation and ice are explained in Drange (1994).

The **alkalinity** A_T can be expressed as (Drange, 1994)

$$A_T = [\text{Na}^+] + 2[\text{Ca}^{2+}] + 2[\text{Mg}^{2+}] + [\text{NH}_4^+] + \dots - [\text{Cl}^-] - 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] - [\text{NO}_3^-] - \dots, \quad (3.36)$$

where $[\]$ denotes the number of moles of the solute per kilogram sea water and A_T is given in terms of charge equivalents (i.e., the ions Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} are multiplied by two). Thus, biological uptake (removal from water) of one concentration unit of NO_3^- results in an increase of one charge unit of A_T . Similarly, biological uptake of one concentration unit of NH_4^+ decreases A_T by one charge unit.

The solution of CaCO_3 in sea water may be written as (e.g., Drange, 1994; Bearman *et al.*, 1995)

where s denotes a solid and aq denotes that the species is dissolved in sea water, respectively. Thus for each concentration unit of CaCO_3 formed, we have from (3.36–3.37) that A_T decreases by two charge units.

The alkalinity equation can now be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_{FDM02}^{AT} &= -\frac{\delta N_n}{\delta t} + \frac{\delta N_r}{\delta t} - 2\frac{\delta \text{CaCO}_3}{\delta t} \\ &= J(\tilde{N}_n - \tilde{N}_r)P - U_2 + \mu_3 B + \epsilon\mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z} - 2\frac{\delta \text{CaCO}_3}{\delta t}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

Adjustments for evaporation and precipitation are also included in the model.

Regeneration model below the photic zone

A nutrient regeneration model is used below the photic zone. To be more specific, the phytoplankton, zooplankton, bacteria and DON compartments decay to ammonium and then to nitrate, and DOC decays to DIC. For all these processes, a constant (and identical) decay rate λ is used. Further, the flux of particulate matter below the photic zone is described by the empirical relationship

$$F(z) = F(z_{pz}) \left(\frac{z}{z_{pz}} \right)^{-\nu}, \quad (3.39)$$

where z_{pz} is the depth of the photic zone and ν is a characteristic parameter. The depth profile of particulate matter can be found from (3.39), and an immediate remineralization of the POM to ammonium is assumed.

3.2.3 The SCH02 formulation

This biogeochemical model version (Schartau, personal communication) includes parameterizations which account for the physiological acclimation of marine phytoplankton to changes in environmental conditions. The basic model approach is adopted from the study of Geider *et al.* (1998). The model effectively decouples carbon from nitrogen fluxes and therefore allows for non-redfield stoichiometric simulations. Phytoplankton growth is strongly regulated by light availability (\mathcal{I}), temperature (T), dissolved nutrient concentrations, and the cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio (q). This regulation of nutrient acquisition by marine phytoplankton, such as the uptake of inorganic dissolved carbon (DIC) and nitrogen (DIN), affects organic carbon and nitrogen fluxes within the entire biogeochemical environment of interest. Therefore, the current basic model version is termed **Carbon to Nitrogen Regulated Ecosystem Model (CN-REcoM)**.

The CN-REcoM consists of five compartments: Nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, detritus and extracellular organic matter (EOM), Figure (3.7). Twelve individual state variables are regarded for representing basic biogeochemical nitrogen and carbon fluxes. The basic version does not include bacteria and therefore the microbial loop is not explicitly resolved. The concentration of *chlorophyll a* of marine phytoplankton is considered as an individual model state variable. The originally proposed formulation of the regulatory terms of Geider *et al.* (1998) have been modified in order to make the model better suitable for coupled physical-biological simulations. With this modification

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Figure 3.7: The CN-REcoM version includes the carbonate system and considers air-sea exchange of carbon dioxide ($p\text{CO}_2$). Zooplankton grazing is explicitly resolved. The carbon content of Transparent Exopolymer Particles (TEP-C) can be accounted for (as a fraction of the EOC pool), as they are anticipated to play a crucial role for particle aggregation and the export of carbon (carbon sequestration).

the regulation dynamics is hardly altered, but the new parameterization has the advantage of making the model more robust. Continuous functions are proposed for regulating carbon acquisition, synthesis of *chlorophyll a*, and nitrogen uptake (\mathcal{R}_{Phot} , \mathcal{R}_{Chl} , and \mathcal{R}_C^N). These functions are valid for any possible molar nitrogen to carbon ratio.

The modeled carbonate chemistry is constrained by two state variables, namely total alkalinity (ALK) and DIC. FORTRAN routines for assessing carbon dioxide (CO_2) concentrations and the corresponding air-sea flux (\mathcal{F}_C) are depicted from the Ocean Carbon-Cycle Model Intercomparison Project (OCMIP), e.g. at al. (2002). These routines of the carbonate system are commonly applied in other models as well. Note that the current model does not regard calcification, the production of particulate inorganic carbon (PIC), and therefore changes in total alkalinity solely depend on the uptake and remineralization of nitrogen and phosphorous. Since phosphorous is not resolved, its effect on total alkalinity is completely determined by the nitrogen dynamics, applying a constant molar nitrogen to phosphorous ratio of 16. The air-sea exchange rates, especially the piston velocity, are parameterized according to Wanninkhof (1992).

CN-REcoM equations

The inorganic compounds DIC and DIN are the source for phytoplankton growth. DIN is either taken up by phytoplankton or mineralized. Hence, the initial nitrogen mass is conserved within the system. This is not the case for the DIC pool which gains or loses mass through air-sea exchange. Total alkalinity is regarded in order to allow for a determination of the partial pressure CO_2 ($p\text{CO}_2$) and its gradient between the atmosphere and the upper water column needed for the exchange rate of DIC (\mathcal{F}_C).

Equations for dissolved inorganic compounds:

$$DIC_t = (r_{phy} - C_{phot}) \cdot PhyC + r_{zoo} \cdot ZooC + \rho_C(T) \cdot (1 - f_{tep}) \cdot EOC + \mathcal{F}_C, \quad (3.40)$$

$$DIN_t = -\frac{V_C^N}{q} \cdot PhyN + \rho_N(T) \cdot EON, \quad (3.41)$$

$$ALK_t = (1 + 1/16) \cdot \left(\frac{V_C^N}{q} \cdot PhyN - \rho_N(T) \cdot EON \right). \quad (3.42)$$

The differential equations of DIC contain the remineralization of labile dissolved organic carbon. This labile fraction ($1 - f_{tep}$) is represented by the extracellular organic carbon (EOC) that is not in colloidal form, as it is found in transparent exopolymer particles (TEP-C). The remineralization of TEP-C happens on longer time scales and is therefore separated from the degradation of labile EOC. Coagulation and degradation of the TEP fraction of EOC is not yet fully implemented to the model presented here. However, f_{tep} can be chosen to be zero and the full EOC pool then becomes subject to rapid remineralization.

Phytoplankton growth represents the conversion of inorganic carbon and nitrogen to organic material. Photosynthesis (C_{phot}) is expressed as a carbon-specific rate. The light saturated photosynthetic

rate is assumed to be a linear function of the cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio (q), meaning that under DIN replete conditions the light saturated photosynthetic rate decreases as q becomes smaller. Subtracting phytoplankton respiration (r_{phy}) from photosynthesis (or carbon acquisition) yields a net photosynthetic rate. The respiration rate is modeled as the sum of a maintenance metabolic rate (r_C) and biosynthetic costs (ζV_C^N). Grazing (\mathcal{G}) and particle aggregation (\mathcal{A}) are the major sinks for phytoplankton biomass. A sinking velocity (v_{phy}) can be assigned to the phytoplankton compartment, in order to simulate the sinking of single phytoplankton cells.

Phytoplankton equations:

$$PhyC_t = (C_{phot} - r_{phy} - \gamma_C) \cdot PhyC - \frac{1}{q} \cdot (\mathcal{G} + \mathcal{A}) - v_{phy} \cdot \frac{\partial PhyC}{\partial z}, \quad (3.43)$$

$$PhyN_t = \left(\frac{V_C^N}{q} - \gamma_N \right) \cdot PhyN - \mathcal{G} - \mathcal{A} - v_{phy} \cdot \frac{\partial PhyN}{\partial z}, \quad (3.44)$$

$$CHL_t = (\mathcal{S}_{chl} - \gamma_{chl}) \cdot CHL - \frac{\theta_C}{q} \cdot (\mathcal{G} + \mathcal{A}) - v_{phy} \cdot \frac{\partial CHL}{\partial z}. \quad (3.45)$$

DIN uptake rates are calculated with a Michaelis-Menten function. The corresponding maximum assimilation rate (V_{max}^C) is carbon-specific and is regulated by the cell quota (q), temperature (T). With increasing nitrogen to carbon ratios the nitrogen assimilation rate is downregulated, in order to prevent an excessive nitrogen uptake by phytoplankton under low light conditions. Grazing rates and aggregation are calculated according the phytoplankton nitrogen biomass and then converted to changes in carbon and *chlorophyll a* concentrations. The synthesis of *chlorophyll a* (\mathcal{S}_{chl}) follows the proposed equations of Geider *et al.* (1996). They suggest to consider the ratio of energy assimilated to energy absorbed for regulation. Hence, low light and nutrient replete conditions favour high rates of *chlorophyll a* synthesis. These rates decline with light saturation and nutrient depletion.

The modeled zooplankton biomass does primarily represent micro-zooplankton. Here, phytoplankton is the only source for zooplankton (\mathcal{G}) and therefore it exclusively depends on the accumulation of phytoplankton biomass and hence on its net growth rates (bottom up control).

Zooplankton equation:

$$ZooC_t = \frac{\mathcal{G}}{q} - r_{zoo} \cdot ZooC - (\Phi_z \cdot ZooN^2) \cdot \frac{ZooC}{ZooN}, \quad (3.46)$$

$$ZooN_t = \mathcal{G} - \Phi_z \cdot ZooN^2. \quad (3.47)$$

A quadratic term simulates the loss to higher predators (e.g. meso-zooplankton). However, due to mass balance reasons, this loss term is redirected to the detritus pool. Such a simplification (zooplankton closure) can be done if one refers to sloppy feeding. Hence, the approach taken here may be interpreted as a grazing loss to meso-zooplankton with a very low ingestion efficiency. The remaining micro-zooplankton fractions or fecal pellets produced by the virtually resolved meso-zooplankton eventually become detritus.

Detritus is modeled as a compartment which represents particulate organic matter that is subject

to remineralization and sinking. Its rates primarily determine the effective flux of carbon and nitrogen to the deep ocean.

Detritus:

$$DetC_t = \frac{\mathcal{A}}{q} + (\Phi_z \cdot ZooN^2) \cdot \frac{ZooC}{ZooN} - \omega_C(T) \cdot DetC - v_{det} \cdot \frac{\partial DetC}{\partial z}, \quad (3.48)$$

$$DetN_t = \mathcal{A} + \Phi_z \cdot ZooN^2 - \omega_N(T) \cdot DetN - v_{det} \cdot \frac{\partial DetN}{\partial z}. \quad (3.49)$$

According to the aggregation equations (A), detritus is nonlinearly linked with phytoplankton biomass, which may induce oscillatory solutions as analyzed by Ruiz *et al.* (2002). All remineralization rates are temperature dependent (ω_N and ω_C). The remineralization rates may be linked according to energy requirements and nutrient demands which would reduce the number of free parameters. The sinking of detritus is modeled with a very sophisticated third order advection scheme with flux delimitation, adopted from the code of the MIT-GCM. In the model presented here, the degraded particulate organic matter becomes dissolved organic matter (EOM) first before it is completely remineralized to become an inorganic substance. However, the model parameters can be chosen such that all remineralized organic matter is transferred through the EOM pool without leading to an accumulation of EOM. If desired and with the appropriate choice of parameter values, the dynamics of that particular compartment can be insignificant.

Extracellular organic matter:

$$EOC_t = \gamma_C \cdot PhyC + \omega_C(T) \cdot DetC - \rho_C(T) \cdot (1 - f_{lep})EOC, \quad (3.50)$$

$$EON_t = \gamma_N \cdot PhyN + \omega_N(T) \cdot DetN - \rho_N(T) \cdot EON. \quad (3.51)$$

Remineralized EOM reenters the inorganic pool of nutrients. By choosing f_{lep} nonzero, not all carbon found in EOC is considered as labile and is therefore retained. Apart from the degradation of detritus, there is a source of EOM coming from the phytoplankton compartment (γ_N and γ_C). These sources depend linearly on phytoplankton biomass and account for leakage, cell lysis. However, active exudation (albeit biomass proportional) can also be attributed to the loss of organic carbon (γ_C). We therefore suggest a parameter combination where γ_C always exceeds γ_N . As for the detrital remineralization rates, the parameters ρ_N and ρ_C can be dynamically linked. Such a dependency could be inferred from nutrient availability (DIN) and the interaction with radiation (\mathcal{I}).

CN-REcoM parameters

Model parameters are separated into those whose values need to be either optimized or to be tuned and others which are thought to remain constant under all conditions. We therefore distinguish between free variational and fixed parameters. Table (3.2.3) lists name and units of the variational parameters together with suggested values for the fixed ones. Some code specific parameters are constants or logical variables which allow some switching between few model configurations. Table (3.2.3) shows

default values of these code specific parameters set in the parameter namelist *REcoM_parameter.list*.

Free (variational) parameters	Symbol	Unit
1. CHL a-specific attenuation coefficient	κ_{chl}	$m^3(mgChla)^{-1}$
2. CHL a-specific initial slope of P-I function	α_{chl}	$mmolC(mgChla)^{-1}m^2W^{-1}d^{-1}$
3. Carbon-specific rate of photosynthesis	μ_C	d^{-1}
4. Half saturation constant of DIN uptake rate	k_N	$mmolNm^{-3}$
5. Factor for carbon-specific rate of nitrate uptake	V_{fact}	dimensionless
6. Phytoplankton maintenance metabolic rate	r_C	d^{-1}
7. Chlorophyll degradation rate	γ_{chl}	d^{-1}
8. Phytoplankton nitrogen loss rate	γ_N	d^{-1}
9. Phytoplankton carbon loss rate	γ_C	d^{-1}
10a. Nitrogen remineralization rate	ρ_N	d^{-1}
10b. Carbon remineralization rate	ρ_C	d^{-1}
11a. Fraction of EOC in TEP-C (optional)	f_{tep}	dimensionless
11b. Fraction of TEP-C not in POC (optional)	f_x	dimensionless
12. Aggregation parameter	Φ_{agg}	$m^3mmolN^{-1}d^{-1}$
13. Detritus carbon degradation rate	ω_C	d^{-1}
14. Detritus nitrogen degradation rate	ω_N	d^{-1}
15. Zooplankton respiration	r_{zoo}	d^{-1}
16. Zooplankton quadratic loss rate	Φ_z	$m^3mmolN^{-1}d^{-1}$
17. Zooplankton maximum grazing rate	g	d^{-1}
18. Zooplankton half saturation capture rate	ϵ	$mmolN^2m^{-6}$
19. Phytoplankton single cell sinking velocity	v_{phy}	md^{-1}
20. Detritus sinking velocity	v_{det}	md^{-1}

Fixed parameters		Value
Cost parameter associated with biosynthesis	ζ	2.0 mmol C mmol N ⁻¹
Molar carbon to nitrogen ratio	<i>Redfield</i>	6.625
Minimum cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio	q_{min}	0.05
Maximum cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio	q_{max}	0.2
Maximum cellular chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio	θ_N^{max}	6.00
Slope parameter for photosynthetic regulation	σ_{phot}	50 mmol N ² mmol C ⁻²
Slope parameter for nitrogen uptake regulation	σ_C^N	1000 mmol N ² mmol C ⁻²
Attenuation coefficient due to water	κ	0.04 m ⁻¹
Slope of Arrhenius relation	A_E	4500 K
Reference temperature for Arrhenius relation	T_{ref}	288.15 K

Specific program parameters	Name used in program	Default
Timestep of internal biological loop	bio_step	10
Number of biogeochemical tracers	bgc_num	12
TEP modifying coagulation efficiency	TEPaggreaqtion	.false.
Evans and Parslow growth function (1985)	EvansParslow	.false.

Some model details

A rigorous description and discussion of the physiological acclimation processes can be found in Geider *et al.* (1998). Model extensions, such as aggregation and grazing, will need a more severe analysis at individual open ocean sites. Nevertheless, the here proposed equations have been successfully applied within a 0D-model version of the upper mixed layer at the site of the North Atlantic Bloom Experiment (47N 20W, Markus Schartau, personal communication).

Temperature function:

$$T_{func} = \exp \left[A_E \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}} \right) \right]. \quad (3.52)$$

Carbon assimilation and respiration of phytoplankton:

$$C_{phot} = \mu_C^{max} \cdot \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\theta_C \cdot \alpha_{chl} \cdot \mathcal{I}}{\mu_C^{max}} \right) \right]. \quad (3.53)$$

Maximum rate of carbon-specific photosynthesis controlled by temperature and the cell quota:

$$\mu_C^{max} = \mu_C \cdot \mathcal{R}_{phot} \cdot T_{func}. \quad (3.54)$$

Regulation as a function of the cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio (q):

$$\mathcal{R}_{phot} = 1 - \exp \left[\sigma_{phot} \cdot (|q_{min} - q| - (q_{min} - q))^2 \right], \quad (3.55)$$

with the slope parameter (σ_{phot}) and the minimum cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio (q_{min}).

Phytoplankton respiration:

$$r_{phy} = r_C + \zeta \cdot V_C^N. \quad (3.56)$$

Grazing:

$$\mathcal{G} = \frac{g \cdot PhyN^2}{\epsilon + PhyN^2} \cdot ZooN. \quad (3.57)$$

Aggregation:

$$\mathcal{A} = \Phi_{agg} \cdot PhyN \cdot DetN. \quad (3.58)$$

Nitrogen assimilation of phytoplankton:

$$V_C^N = V_C^{max} \cdot \frac{DIN}{DIN + k_N}. \quad (3.59)$$

Maximum rate of carbon-specific nitrate uptake controlled by temperature and the cell quota:

$$V_C^{max} = (V_{fact} \cdot \mu_C^{max} \cdot q_{max}) \cdot \mathcal{R}_C^N \cdot T_{func}. \quad (3.60)$$

Regulation as a function of the cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio:

$$\mathcal{R}_C^N = 1 - \exp \left[\sigma_C^N \cdot (|q - q_{max}| - (q - q_{max}))^2 \right], \quad (3.61)$$

with the slope parameter (σ_C^N) and the maximum cellular nitrogen to carbon ratio (q_{max}).

Chlorophyll synthesis:

$$S_{chl} = \frac{V_C^N}{\theta_C} \cdot \mathcal{R}_{chl}. \quad (3.62)$$

Regulation as a function of maximum chlorophyll a to nitrogen ratio and light (energy) utilization:

$$\mathcal{R}_{chl} = \min \left[\theta_N^{max}, \theta_N^{max} \left(\frac{C_{phot}}{\theta_C \cdot \alpha_{chl} \cdot \mathcal{I}} \right) \right]. \quad (3.63)$$

The assigned minimum simply prevents the model from generating values for \mathcal{R}_{chl} that exceed θ_N^{max} under tiny light conditions, as they are found in the deep ocean in the absence of phytoplankton biomass and unreasonable or non existing chlorophyll to carbon ratios (θ_C).

3.3 An example with the FDM02 model

This section contains an example of the coupled HYCOM-ecosystem model, using the FDM02 formulation for describing the ecosystem.

The model system was set up for the North Atlantic using the orthogonal curvilinear grid shown in figure 3.8. Note that the poles have been mapped to new locations, i.e., to avoid having a singularity at the North Pole and to increase the grid resolution in the North Atlantic. The model uses a relaxation scheme (towards climatology) at the various open ocean boundaries, i.e., in the South Atlantic, the Mediterranean, the Baltic Sea and the Hudson Bay. The connection to the Pacific Ocean has also been shut off by closing the Bering Strait.

The HYCOM restart file was taken from other simulations within the ToPAZ project, while we use very simple initial conditions for the biochemistry. To be more specific, the following surface values were defined: $P = 0.14 \text{ mmol N m}^{-3}$, $Z = B = 0.014 \text{ mmol N m}^{-3}$, $N_r = N_d = D_N = 0.1 \text{ mmol N m}^{-3}$, and $C_d = D_C = 0.7 \text{ mmol C m}^{-3}$. The carbon based initial values have been calculated from the corresponding nitrogen based, using the Redfield carbon to nitrogen ratio of

Figure 3.8: *The orthogonal curvilinear grid.*

Figure 3.9: The figure shows the surface distribution of phytoplankton [mmol N m^{-3}] and the current pattern in the Gulf Stream for day 105 in 1997. Three large scale eddies can be observed; note especially how phytoplankton rich water near the coast is advected into them, initiating the formation of so-called Gulf Stream rings (the current grid resolution is not fully eddy-resolving, i.e., higher resolution should be used for a detailed study of the eddies). The advection scheme used in the experiment is new and has been developed by Y. Morel and coworkers at NERSC, and it produces very smooth fields compared to the standard HYCOM approach.

phytoplankton. Thus, the free floating DON/DOC and PON/POC ratios are initialized using the corresponding ratio of phytoplankton. At greater depths, the phytoplankton, zooplankton, bacteria, ammonium, DON and DOC compartments are assumed to decrease exponentially according to a characteristic layer index of 10.

The presentation given here will be limited to include the first few months of the model evolution. Since the biochemical model will need 2–3 years to enter a stable cycle, the results will only provide a first qualitative assessment of the dynamical behavior of the ecosystem.

We start by showing the surface distribution of phytoplankton and the current pattern in the Gulf stream region for day 105 in 1997 in Figure 3.9. Three large scale eddies can be observed, and it can be seen how characteristic Gulf Stream rings are formed by advecting phytoplankton into these eddies. The new advection scheme developed at NERSC by Y. Morel and coworkers provides smooth and nice fields without the noise which could be seen in corresponding plots using the standard HYCOM advection scheme. It should be mentioned that the current model grid resolution is not strictly eddy resolving, and thus a detailed study of the eddies would require higher resolution.

Figure 3.10 shows surface layer concentrations of phytoplankton for the initial time (1997 day 0)

and at the days 7, 28, 63, 91 and 119, respectively. A large “artificial” bloom is triggered by the model in the South Atlantic. The reason for this is probably because the initial ecosystem (i.e., the initial conditions) is not well balanced. That is, allowing phytoplankton to exist initially under such favorable light and nutrient conditions triggers an immediate bloom. However, the artificial bloom soon collapses, and the model enters a more realistic cycle. A positive result is that a realistic (at least qualitatively) North Atlantic spring bloom of phytoplankton evolves northwards, reaching the Nordic Seas in the end of March/ beginning of April.

The surface concentrations of nitrate are shown in Figure 3.11 for the same times as for phytoplankton. It is clearly seen how the dynamics between the nitrate and phytoplankton compartments work: during the large South Atlantic “artificial” bloom of phytoplankton, all the surface nitrate is utilized for the growth. The same is seen for the North Atlantic bloom, where increased phytoplankton concentrations lead to low nitrate concentrations. During winter time, the surface nitrate concentrations will start to build up again, mainly by mixing from nutrient rich water in the deep ocean.

Figure 3.12 shows the corresponding concentrations of zooplankton. As expected, the phytoplankton blooms are closely followed by corresponding zooplankton blooms, which occur a little later since they need the phytoplankton to grow.

Concentrations of organic matter (dissolved and particulate) are shown in Figure 3.13. Particulate matter may come from dead organisms, excretion, etc., and may sink towards the bottom or be broken down to dissolved material. For a detailed description of the dynamical relations involved, see the FDM section.

Depth profiles of phytoplankton for a section at 40°N is shown in Figure 3.14. It is seen that the too large concentrations of phytoplankton in the deep ocean specified initially disappear after a few weeks. Later, the North Atlantic spring bloom can be seen in the few uppermost layers of the model, starting in the west and moving slowly towards the east of the basin.

Figure 3.10: Surface layer concentrations of phytoplankton [mmol N m^{-3}]. The specified initial value (day 0 in 1997) is shown in the top left plot, followed by the concentrations for day 7 (top, right), day 28 (middle, left), day 63 (middle, right), day 91 (bottom, left) and day 119 (bottom, right), respectively. It is interesting to see how fast the model responds to the initial distributions in the South Atlantic, where an “artificial” large bloom is seen after only 7 days. Then, the situation settles down, before a North Atlantic spring bloom starts near the North African coast, and then spreading northwards reaching the Nordic Seas around day 100.

Figure 3.11: Surface layer concentrations of nitrates [mmol N m^{-3}]. The specified initial value (day 0 in 1997) is shown in the top left plot, followed by the concentrations for day 7 (top, right), day 28 (middle, left), day 63 (middle, right), day 91 (bottom, left) and day 119 (bottom, right), respectively. The dynamical relationship between phytoplankton and nitrate is clearly seen: the “artificial” phytoplankton bloom after a week results in low surface nitrate concentrations over the same domain. This is also seen for the North Atlantic phytoplankton bloom going northwards. Nitrate concentrations will build up again during winter from deep water mixing.

Figure 3.12: Surface layer concentrations of zooplankton [mmol N m^{-3}]. The specified initial value (day 0 in 1997) is shown in the top left plot, followed by the concentrations for day 7 (top, right), day 28 (middle, left), day 63 (middle, right), day 91 (bottom, left) and day 119 (bottom, right), respectively. It is seen that the phytoplankton spring bloom is followed by a little later zooplankton bloom, as expected since the zooplankton grows on the primary producers.

Figure 3.13: Surface layer concentrations of dissolved organic matter (top) and particulate organic matter (bottom) for 1997 day 63 (left) and day 119 (right).

Figure 3.14: Depth profiles of phytoplankton for a 40°N section. The top left plot shows the initial distribution (day 0 in 1997), then followed by the situation for the days 7 (row 1 column 2), 14 (r1 c3), 21 (r2 c1), 77 (r2 c2), 84 (r2 c3), 91 (r3 c1), 98 (r3 c2), 105 (r3 c3) and 112 (r4 c2), respectively. During the first three weeks, deep phytoplankton concentrations set initially disappear. Later, a bloom is seen in the few uppermost layers, starting in the middle of March.

Chapter 4

Summary

A general and flexible system for coupling different biochemical formulations to HYCOM has been developed. In this system, the formulations for the tracer advection, mixing and biochemical “regridding” are formulated to work with any formulation for the biochemistry, i.e., performed in loops over the number of tracer compartments. Thus, the only model specific routines are those involving the biochemical sources and sinks.

So far, three different biochemical formulations are embedded into the system: a simple three component NPZ-type model based on Evans and Parslow (1985), an FDM-type model based on Drange (1994), and a new open ocean formulation being developed in ToPAZ by M. Schartau and coworkers at AWI. The two first formulations have been validated for the North Atlantic, while the third has been implemented but not yet validated. Since these three models are typically open ocean formulations, any coastal application will require the embedding of an appropriate biochemical module into the system.

As an example, this report includes some first results of the HYCOM-FDM model, set up for the North Atlantic using one of the standard curvilinear grids in ToPAZ. The results showed that the model was able to simulate a quite realistic spring bloom of phytoplankton (at least qualitatively) at the first simulation year, although one must expect two to three years of simulation before the annual cycle is stable. We also used this example to study briefly the (close) dynamical relationships between phytoplankton and some of the other compartments.

The flexible coupling between HYCOM and the biochemistry allows for a simple switching between different biochemical formulations, i.e., just by switching a flag indicating which formulation to run. Thus, this is an ideal platform to intercompare different biochemical models forced by identical physics provided by HYCOM. Note also that by building up an ensemble of different biochemical formulations in the system, it will be possible to choose a formulation suitable for a specific application, e.g., based on short experiments with the most relevant alternatives before choosing the final biochemical formulation.

Appendix A

Setting up and running a coupled model

This appendix contains a technical description of the model code distribution. The information should be of great help for anyone who wants to set up and use the coupled HYCOM-biochemical model, and also for further extending the system to include alternative formulations for the ecosystem. We start by describing the code distribution and setup in Section A.1, while Section A.2 provides some useful hints for getting the executable to run. Finally, Section A.3 illustrates how to embed alternative biochemical formulations into the coupled model system. Detailed information about the HYCOM source code can be obtained from Bleck *et al.* (2002).

A.1 Code setup

A.1.1 The code distribution

An illustration of the NERSC coupled HYCOM-biochemical system is shown in Figure 3.1. Note that (a few) necessary and general definitions are contained in a single module which always must be present, while further model specific definitions are included as model specific modules. Also, note that the routines for advection, mixing and ecosystem regridding are model independent, while the specific biochemical sources and sinks are included as separate routines for each formulation. Further details are given in the following.

The module *mod_necessary_ecovars.F90* must always be included in the source code, containing the few necessary definitions for the biochemistry. That is, without this module properly defined your coupled model will crash. The source code is as follows:

```
module mod_necessary_ecovars

    use mod_dimensions
    use mod_common

    implicit none

!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
```

```

!
! * * * I M P O R T A N T * * *
!
! The variables in this module must be defined for ANY biochemical model
! coupled to HYCOM, i.e., same names, and with nbio set to the correct
! number of compartments in your model and eco_tag set to a 5 character
! tag for your model.
!
!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

#ifdef EVA85
    integer, parameter :: nbio=3          ! number of biochemical compartments
    character(len=5) :: eco_tag='EVA85' ! tag for the current ecomodel
#endif
#ifdef FDM02
    integer, parameter :: nbio=11       ! number of biochemical compartments
    character(len=5) :: eco_tag='FDM02' ! tag for the current ecomodel
#endif
#ifdef SCH02
    integer, parameter :: nbio=12       ! number of biochemical compartments
    character(len=5) :: eco_tag='SCH02' ! tag for the current ecomodel
#endif

integer, parameter :: nphys1=1 !number of physical steps per biochemical
                                !used for advection and vertical mixing
integer, parameter :: nphys2=1 !number of physical steps per biochemical
                                !used for the biochem. sources and sinks
real biodt1 ! time step - used for advection and vertical mixing:
            != baclin*nphys1 set in hycom.F90
real biodt2 ! time step - used for the biochem. sources and sinks:
            != baclin*nphys2

real bio(nbio,2*kdm,idm,jdm) ! biochemical compartments

real p_old2(idm,jdm,kdm+1) ! workspace

end module mod_necessary_ecovars

```

The *#ifdef* statements are part of the preprocessing, and determined by the contents of the file *MODEL.CPP* (see the next subsection about the compilation). The only model dependent definitions above are *nbio* and *eco_tag*. Once these are set according to a specific model choice (e.g., EVA85, FDM02,...), the correct amount of space will be allocated for the variable *bio* containing all the biochemical compartments. Note that the rest of the definitions are model independent.

In the current version of the code, there is a possibility to run the biochemistry and HYCOM with different time steps. In fact, the parameter *nphys1* determines the time step for the biochemical advection and mixing, while *nphys2* is the step for the sources and sinks, respectively. The parameters

nphys1 and *nphys2* can be tuned to minimize the CPU-requirements, which will be important for applications with large numerical constraints.

Additional biochemical definitions are all model specific, and are gathered in separate modules for each specific formulation. The file name convention is *mod_XXXXY_name.F90*, where *XXXXY* is a model index (e.g., EVA85, FDM02, ...) and *name* is a descriptive name. For example, the EVA85 model contains two modules:

mod_EVA85_bioparameters.F90: Contains definitions of the model parameters.

mod_EVA85_biovariables.F90: Contains the definitions of all variables needed in the model.

Similarly, the FDM02 model contains three such modules:

mod_FDM02_bioparameters.F90: Contains the model parameters.

mod_FDM02_biovariables.F90: Contains the model variables.

mod_FDM02_common_src.F90: Contains some variables for accumulating sources and sinks.

The SCH model has two modules:

mod_SCH02_REcoM_para_def.F90: Contains parameter definitions.

mod_SCH02_biovariables.F90: Contains specific model variables.

Note that the above model specific modules may include a use statement to the always defined module *mod_necessary_ecovars.F90*, e.g., needing to access the number of compartments for further array definitions.

An important property of the system shown in Figure 3.1 is that the routines for advection, vertical mixing and ecosystem regridding are model independent, i.e., they are written in a general way and need not be updated for a new biochemical formulation. Advection and mixing of the biochemistry is included by updating the standard HYCOM routines *m_tsadvc.F* and *m_mxkppaij.F*, respectively. The processes can be called in loops over the number of compartments, i.e., to update the general *bio* variable which is accessible from the always defined module *mod_necessary_ecovars.F90*. The details of the biochemical regridding (including the source code of *m_regrid_ecosys.F90*) was provided in Section 3.1.3.

The biochemical sources and sinks will of course be dependent on the specific biochemical formulation. Thus, a set of routines for each biochemical model must be implemented. As seen from Figure 3.1, these routines will be dependent on the model specific definitions as well as the general module *mod_necessary_ecovars.F90*. The name convention for these routine is *m_XXXXY_name.F90*, where *XXXXY* again is a model index (e.g., EVA85, FDM02, ...) and *name* is a descriptive name, respectively. For example, the EVA85 model has the following specific routines:

m_EVA85_biochm_init.F90: Model initialization.

m_EVA85_alpha.F90: Calculates the specific growth rate of phytoplankton, i.e., the light limited growth as a function of surface irradiance and depth.

m_EVA85_biochm.F90: The main routine for the biochemistry loop, e.g., updating time variables, calling for the updated light limited growth rate, and calling for the sources and sinks.

m_EVA85_bclsys.F90: Calculates the biochemical sources and sinks and updating the model variables for a given time step.

m_EVA85_nconservation.F90: A simple routine for calculating the total amount of nitrogen in the model. Very useful for debugging!

The following specific routines have been implemented for the FDM02 model:

m_FDM02_biochm_init.F: Model initialization.

m_FDM02_biochm.F90: Main routine for the biochemistry loop; the other routines are called by this routine in each step of the time loop.

m_FDM02_bclkpz.F: Determines the euphotic zone depth, i.e., the number of layers considered to be in the euphotic zone. This is later used to ensure that the active ecosystem model is used in the photic zone, while a simple nutrient regeneration model is used below.

m_FDM02_biosun.F: Computes the surface irradiance from the sun. The model uses the 24 hours mean value, calculated as PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) in W/m^2 .

m_FDM02_bclpgr.F: Computes the light limited phytoplankton growth rate.

m_FDM02_bclsnk.F: Computes the amount of sinking particles in the water column.

m_FDM02_eminp_adj.F: Considers the evaporation minus precipitation, and updates the alkalinity and inorganic carbon compartments accordingly.

m_FDM02_bclsys.F: This routine computes all the sources and sinks in the biochemical model.

m_FDM02_biochm1.F: Chemistry module; calculates the chemical equilibrium constants, the concentration of borate, the schmidt number of CO_2 in sea water and the gas exchange velocity.

m_FDM02_pco2_functions.F90: Contains some functions for determining the concentration of CO_2 in the atmosphere.

m_FDM02_pco2atm.F: Calculates the amount of CO_2 in the atmosphere.

m_FDM02_bioco2.F: Calculates the flux of CO_2 across the air-ocean boundary.

m_FDM02_bioout.F: Outputs all the parameter values to the screen.

m_FDM02_bclneg1.F: Checks if all the biochemical compartments are positive.

m_FDM02_nconservation.F90: Computes the total amount of nitrogen in the model.

For the SCH02 model, the following specific routines have been implemented:

m_SCH02_REcoM_para_read.F90: Reads model parameters from file 'REcoM_parameter.list'.

m_SCH02_biochm.F90: The main routine controlling the time stepping and containing the sms call.

m_SCH02_REcoM_sms.F90: Basic source minus sink module; includes sinking of phytoplankton and detritus (see flag to be set in 'REcoM_parameter.list')

m_SCH02_init_bgc_tracer.F90: Initialization of biological tracer field (optional, GCM dependend, not used for now but can be used to make an initial restart file).

m_SCH02_radia_diurnal.F90: Generates diurnal cycle of radiation for given noon irradiance (optional).

m_SCH02_daylength.F90: Determines the daylength for a given day of the year at a specified latitude from an astronomical formula (optional).

m_SCH02_brock_reed.F90: Determines surface radiation at noon for a given day of the year at a specified latitude from an astronomical formula (optional).

m_SCH02_T_func.F90: Temperature dependance of maximum rates.

m_SCH02_C_photosynthesis.F90: Light limited growth rate.

m_SCH02_N_assimilation.F90: Carbon-specific nitrogen uptake.

m_SCH02_CHL_synth_reg.F90: Regulation of chlorophyll synthesis.

m_SCH02_co2flux.F90: Air-Sea flux of CO₂; determination of pH; transformation of CO₂ to units mmol m⁻³; (OCMIP code; modifications by Christoph Voelker and Markus Schartau); the following routines are called for:

m_SCH02_co2calc.F90

m_SCH02_drtsafe.F90

m_SCH02_schmidt.F90

m_SCH02_wann.F90

m_SCH02_ta_iter_simple.F

m_SCH02_recom_sinking.F90: Third order advection scheme with flux correction (code adopted from MIT-GCM and implemented by Martin Losch, personal communication)

using CPP pre-processing is obvious; it simply allows the user to turn on and off specific parts of the code, while keeping the code distribution as general as possible.

The details of how to set up the makefile is beyond the scope of this report, this may be done in different ways which is also dependent on the computer platform. At NERSC, the code is currently compiled and run on an IBM Regatta machine using the UNIX platform. The makefile is configured to compile the code in three steps: The first is done by typing *make source*, calling a script which scans the code and sorting the files depending on whether they are modules, f77 files, f90 files, etc., writing this information to the file *source.files*. The second step is done by typing *make depend*, calling a script which creates a file *depends.file* containing the dependencies of the various modules and routines. Then, the final step *make* compiles the code. For a successful compilation, one should now have an executable file.

A.2 Running the model

This section contains some short remarks about running the code after compilation has been successfully completed and the executable exists.

A.2.1 Necessary files and setup

Let us start by looking at some files which will be needed before you can start the model integration.

Atmospheric forcing: Currently, the NERSC system uses 6 hourly fields provided by ECMWF. A link to the directory which contains the forcing fields must be created.

HYCOM restart file: Contains the full HYCOM model state, or an ensemble of states for ensemble runs. The file name is *XXXrestartYYYY_DDD_HH.uf*, where *XXX* is a three character model tag, *YYYY* the year, *DDD* the day and *HH* the hour, respectively. Note that the restart file is binary. Thus, it cannot be viewed directly or moved to another computer platform.

ICE restart file: Must be present if ice is included. File name is *XXXrestartYYYY_DDD_HHICE.uf*

ECO restart file: Must be present for ecosystem simulations. Note that this restart file must also be the correct version, depending on whether we have the EVA85 model, the FDM02 model, and so on. File name will be *XXXrestartYYYY_DDD_HHECO_EEEEE.uf*, where *EEEEEE* is the ecosystem model flag, i.e., EVA85, FDM02, and so on, depending on which ecosystem formulation you are running.

infile.in: This file is the main configuration file for your model run. For example, it may look like:

```
2.9          # version of inputfile (limits.dat) DO NOT CHANGE
T1H         # (rungen) model tag
T           # (restart) Start from restart file (nday1 > 0)
```

```

1995      # Reference year for simulation (0000 for spinup)
  000 00  # (nday1) First day of integration NOTE FORMAT F9.2
  001 00  # (nday2) Last day of integration NOTE FORMAT F9.2
  1 1    # imem1, imem2 range of ensemble members to integrate
file      # reading latlon from file
ecmwf     # forcing option, month, ecmwf, ncepr, waner
  60.0    # temperature relaxation time scale
  60.0    # salinity relaxation time scale
  450.0   # baroclinic time step
  45.0    # barotropic time step
F 12     # print forcing functions from month 1 to ?
F 1      # leverage n Accumulate weekly averages every n hours
F        # Accumulate section transports
F 6      # lnesto, nestdto - saves nesting bnd cond at nestdto int
F 6      # lnesti, nestdti - read&apply nesting bnd cond at nestdti int
F CSR F F # Tides (true, CSR/FES, apply currents, slowstart)
F        # Add river fluxes
F        # lparticle Integrating particles or not
F        # lgridp Activate storage of gridpoint information
F 4      # lmovie n Dumps movie file every n hours
# Days    Assi  Diagno.  Restart
      0 00  F      T      F
      1 00  F      T      F

```

The most important settings include the year and start/end day of the integration, the (baroclinic and barotropic) time step, as well as the diagnostic and restart output times set at the bottom.

infile2.in: Also a configuration file, which is used for setting up random forcing during ensemble runs. It may look like:

```

1.1      # version of inputfile (infile2.in)
false    # (randf)   Random forcing
1        # (seed)    seed to random number generator
0.25    # (taux)    Variance in tau_x
0.25    # (tauy)    Variance in tau_y
250000.0 # (wndspd)    Variance in wndspd
2.5E-05 # (radflx)    Variance in radflx
25.0    # (airtmp)   Variance in airtmp
0.0     # (precip)   Variance in precip
0.0     # (vapmix)   Variance in vapmix

```

Note that the *false* statement will turn off the random forcing, while a *true* statement will turn it on, i.e., adding noise to the atmospheric fields using the above variances.

Topography file: This contains the ocean depths as interpolated onto your model grid. File name is *depthsIIIxJJJ.uf*, where *III* and *JJJ* are the grid dimensions.

Longitude/latitude file: Contains the lon/lat values of all the grid points of your model grid. File name is *newpos.uf* or *newposIIIxJJJ.uf*.

HYCOM configuration file: File name is *blkdat.input*. This is the correct file if you want to play with the HYCOM configuration, e.g., the vertical discretization setup.

grid.info: This file contains information about your specific grid and may look like

```

-10.0 140.0      ! Position of pole N (latitude, longitude):
-30.0 140.0      ! Position of pole S (latitude, longitude):
175.0 187.0 400 ! Longitude interval West lon, East lon, idim
   3.0  80.0 600 ! Latitude interval south limit, north limit, jdim
.true.           ! Generate topography
.true.           ! dump teclatlon.dat
.true.           ! dump micom latlon.dat
.true.           ! mercator grid (true, false)
-8.0 .false.     ! merc fac
.false.         ! Smoothing, Shapiro filter
8  2             ! Order of Shapiro filter, number of passes

```

REcoM_parameter.list: Contains the parameter values for the SCH02 model.

If you have the correct versions of all the files mentioned above, you should be ready to start the model integration.

A.2.2 Starting the model run and looking at the output

The model can either be run interactively, or preferably by using a batch queue system if that exists on the computer system. One should always start out by checking that the model reads all input files correctly, and that the fields look reasonable after a few time steps. Then, you will be sure that the model starts out realistically before proceeding with further integration over larger time intervals.

The NERSC system provides output files at all times specified at the bottom of the *infile.in* file. The output is written to a file *XXXyYYYYdDDDhHH*, where *XXX* again is the model flag, *YYYY* the year, *DDD* the day and *HH* the hour, respectively. A corresponding header file *XXXyYYYYd-DDDhHH.hdr* is also output. By setting up an *extract.ext* file, where *ext* is a version flag extension, a file *tmp1.plt* can be created by running a script *m2t -ext XXXyYYYYdDDDhHH*. The *tmp1.plt* file can be viewed in *tecplot*. The *extract.ext* file may look like:

```

3                # Version of teconv program
  DP             # Field used to determine layer interfaces
2 T T F         # 2-D, sphere, rotate, index velocities
1 210 1 270     # section plot ia:ib ja:jb
1 1  XX XX  X   # extracted layers for 3-d fields (not used for 2-d)
  SSH  1  1  F
UBAVG  1  1  F
VBAVG  1  1  F

```

PBAVG	1	1	F
FICEM	1	1	F
HICEM	1	1	F
HSNWM	1	1	F
TICEM	1	1	F
TSRFM	1	1	F
UICE	1	1	F
VICE	1	1	F
PCO2A	1	1	F
PCO2W	1	1	F
CO2FX	1	1	F
GASEX	1	1	F
DP	1	1	T
TEM	1	1	T
SAL	1	1	T
UT	1	1	F
VT	1	1	F
PHYPL	1	5	T
ZOOPL	1	5	T
BACTA	1	5	T
NITR	1	5	T
AMMON	1	5	T
DON	1	5	T
PON	1	5	T
DOC	1	5	T
POC	1	5	T
DIC	1	5	T
ALK	1	5	T

The list ensures that those variables marked by T are plotted. In the example above, PHYPL to ALK will be plotted from layer 1 to 5, while only the surface layer will be plotted for DP, TEM and SAL.

A.3 Embedding a new biochemical model in the distribution

This section contains some comments about how to add a new biochemical formulation to the distribution. Please reconsider Figure 3.1, which is an illustration of the biochemical coupling to HYCOM. As said before, the routines for horizontal advection and diffusion, vertical mixing and ecosystem re-gridding are model independent, and will work for any biochemical formulation embedded into the system. However, the following routines will have to be updated:

mod.necessary_ecovars.F90: Must be updated to include the new model, i.e., the number of compartments must be set as well as the model character flag.

Model dependent ecosystem definitions: All model specific definitions for the formulation to be

embedded must be written in separate modules. The name convention is *mod_XXXXY_name.F90*, where *XXXXY* is the model index for the new model and *name* is a descriptive name. The same model index *XXXXY* should be used in the *MODEL.CPP* file for compiling the correct parts of the code.

Sources and sinks: All specific routines for the model sources and sinks must be written in separate module routines. The name convention is *m_XXXXY_name.F*.

Other small changes: A quick search for *#ifdef ECOSYS* will determine if there are other places where someone has implemented something model dependent. If so, add your version to fit your particular model formulation.

Once these updates have been made, the new model can be activated in *MODEL.CPP*, and you are ready to compile and run.

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